

THE PROBLEM OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING IN THE THEORY OF PSYCHOLOGY

Yakubova Barno Baxtiyorovna

Senior Lecturer of the "Department
of Languages and Humanities",
Andijan State Technical Institute

b.yakubova 1990@gmail.com,+99877-037-00-57

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Annotation. This article discusses the theory of psychology, ongoing changes in the education sector of our country, students' independent learning, the active participation of students in developing their personal knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as the processes of acquiring knowledge without the help of a teacher. This process contributes to the development of students' critical thinking skills, sense of responsibility, and creative approaches. Through independent learning, students have the opportunity to expand their knowledge, conduct independent research, and apply new knowledge in practice. To improve the effectiveness of independent learning in pedagogical research, the leadership of educators, methodological support, and effective use of information technologies are important. Additionally, teaching students to learn independently and increasing their motivation in this process are crucial factors in addressing this issue.

Keywords: knowledge, skills, abilities, competence, technology, education, science, production, psychological goal, educator, upbringing.

The changes taking place in the education sector of our country, namely the laws and decrees adopted, undoubtedly have a positive impact on the development of our society. They are an important factor in increasing the country's intellectual potential and in preparing qualified, competitive specialists who can meet the requirements of the state education standards.

Independent learning is an important factor in becoming a qualified specialist. This is especially evident in the system of professional training. Our ancestors also valued the acquisition of vocational skills by the younger generation and their development into well-educated, cultured individuals who serve progress.[1]

Independence is one of the positive traits of a person's character, reflected in their system of thinking, various activities, and actions. The concept of independence is related to the idea of freedom in choosing ways and means to solve the tasks faced by a person.[2]

At every stage of a person's life, their level of independence manifests in a unique way. This level of independence can be higher or lower depending on the conditions and needs of the person's development.

The striving to independently acquire knowledge is the most distinctive feature of student activity in an educational institution and serves as the foundation for learning and gaining knowledge on one's own. The process of independent study and knowledge acquisition means that students prepare themselves independently.

Today, this sensible approach to education once again proves the great thinker K.D. Ushinsky's idea: "Not being able to express one's thoughts well is a flaw; but not having independent thoughts is an even worse flaw; independent thoughts arise only from

independently acquired knowledge.” Certainly, the famous psychologist L.A. Artsimovich was absolutely right when he said, “A student is not a vessel to be filled with knowledge, but a torch to be ignited.” Living in the information age, today’s youth are very curious and capable of searching for information they desire and find necessary; this is no longer a problem. However, guiding them, advising them, stimulating their interest in the process, and helping them engage in useful work without wasting time have become one of the most important tasks of modern pedagogy. [3]

In foreign theory and practice, the term “Learning autonomy” is studied in connection with concepts such as independent study/learning, self-study, self-directed study/learning, self-access, and self-education. Experience shows that each of these concepts is studied separately. Below, we pay attention to the Uzbek translations of these terms:

- independent study/learning – mustaqil ta’lim olish, sinfdan tashqari ish (independent learning, extracurricular work);
- self-study – mustaqil ish (independent work);
- self-directed study/learning – mustaqil, o’zi individual jadval asosida o’qib bilim orttirish (independent learning following an individual schedule);
- work in self-access centres – axborot resurs markazlarida ishlash (working in information resource centers);
- self-education – o’zi mustaqil o’qish bilan shug’ullanmoq (engaging in independent study).

Observations and practice show that the concepts of independent learning, independent work, and engaging in self-study are used more frequently.

When discussing independent work, first of all, questions arise such as: Is the task assigned during the lesson or outside the classroom? Is it done with the teacher’s help or independently?[4]

The term “Learning autonomy” was first introduced by Henry Holec. This concept refers to the learner’s independence from the teacher or the learner taking responsibility for their own education. It is defined as “autonomy is the ability to take charge of one’s own learning,” meaning active participation in setting the goals and objectives of education, assessing one’s knowledge, skills, and competencies, and engaging in independent learning. Thus, this term is used in a broader sense than simply homework or tasks assigned by the teacher.[5]

Analyses show that scholars have different definitions of independent work and independent learning. V.P. Esipov defines independent work as a task given by the teacher with a fixed completion time, checked either in written or oral form; however, he also points out that such a form of independent work involves “a compulsion to think.” T.I.Shamova emphasizes the clarity of the goals and objectives of independent work, how the results should be presented, the criteria for evaluation, and the necessity of active participation of every student.[6]

I. Unt notes that when a teacher assigns independent work, attention should be paid to its relevance to the covered topic. Furthermore, the scholar rightly points out that independent work is done under the teacher’s supervision but not with their direct involvement. Confirming the above views, it should be noted that any independent work must require the student to think deeply, work regularly on themselves, and engage in critical thinking.[7]

Examples of students' independent work outside classroom time include: taking notes, writing annotations for books and articles, composing summaries and reviews, and writing critiques of websites related to the topic.[8]

Analyzing existing independent work on a given topic available online and evaluating it; writing one's own version or a specific part of a lecture plan; preparing a report on the topic; conducting discussions related to the topic; working on web quests prepared by the teacher or found online; uploading reports and reviews completed by students on a website; creating web quests for the topic and placing them on the course-related website.[9]

In our opinion, it is advisable to strictly adhere to certain criteria when organizing independent work:

- ✓ The form of organizing the work, assignments, and the plan should be developed in consultation with the student;
- ✓ Assignments should be related to the student's real interests, lifestyle, age characteristics, and, of course, aimed at reinforcing the studied topic;
- ✓ Each independent work should help develop the student's self-management, self-development, and self-assessment skills;
- ✓ Assignments should be thought-provoking, problem-oriented, and require creative activity;
- ✓ The content of the assignment should encourage critical thinking and independent reasoning;
- ✓ It is very important that the assignments correspond to the student's knowledge level and motivate them to engage in independent activity.[10]

In conclusion, every lesson should encourage the student to work independently. By engaging in independent activity, the learner consciously understands the essence of their actions, develops intellectually, and takes responsibility for their work.

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